

Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay¹.

H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018. Grant Agreement no. 823961

Interview Report

Dear interviewer,

Please use this document to report on the expert interviews. Please do not summarize more than one interview per interview report. Wherever you have added questions, please add them also in this Interview Report. For any questions or concerns, please contact your local coordinator or logov@eurac.edu

Thank you very much!

Informed consent

See *informed consent sheet*

Can identifying information be shared with LoGov researchers?	[yes]
Use of real name for quotes?	[yes]
Archiving of non-anonymized audio-recording	[yes]
Archiving of anonymized transcript of recording	[yes]
Archiving of anonymized interview report	[yes]

Basic information

Date of the interview	28/07/2021
Name of the interviewer	JORGE CASTILLO ABELLA
[Name of the expert, check consent above]	CARLOS BLÁZQUEZ RODRÍGUEZ
Affiliation of the expert	MUNICIPALITY OF COLMENAR VIEJO
Position/Job description	DEPUTY MAYOR OF COLMENAR VIEJO
Gender	MALE
Years of experience	
Area of expertise	LOCAL POLICIES AND SERVICES
Rural and/or urban focus	RURAL AND URBAN

Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay¹.

H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018. Grant Agreement no. 823961

Part A: Introduction and General Questions

INTERPLAY BETWEEN URBAN AND RURAL MUNICIPAL GOVERNMENTS

1	In your opinion, what is the impact that increasing population movements from the countryside to cities have on local governments?
	The most relevant change that is being seen is, on the one hand, the attraction of the population to the Community of Madrid from other provinces, but, on the other hand, a centrifugal trend from Madrid to other towns within the region, such as Colmenar Viejo. This has been accentuated by the situation of the pandemic in the last year.
2	<p><i>Do you know any public policies or best practices regarding the changing urban-rural relationships? Please consider practices in the following five areas:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Local responsibilities and public services.</i> - <i>Local financial arrangements.</i> - <i>Structure of local government.</i> - <i>Intergovernmental relations of local governments.</i> - <i>People's participation in local decision-making.</i>
	A very relevant practice in the field of public service provision is waste management through the creation of associations. There is also an interesting initiative in the area of the Community of Madrid to create a housing plan, but the priority is not so much to serve the rural-urban axis as to create housing where it is possible and / or more efficient.
3	To retain and, where appropriate, attract population to rural municipalities, is it more important to invest in infrastructure or to improve (or at least maintain) the provision of public services?
	These factors are not mutually exclusive. It is necessary to improve the infrastructures (for the population to arrive), but also to optimize their quality of life in the (rural) municipality. This has been clearly seen with the demographic movements that have occurred as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic towards rural areas, but which demand technological services.

¹ This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 823961.

Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay¹.

H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018. Grant Agreement no. 823961

	However, if there is a choice between infrastructure or public services, the latter are more important when it comes to attracting population to rural areas.
--	---

GENERAL ISSUES REGARDING PUBLIC RESPONSIBILITIES AND PUBLIC SERVICES

4	Indicate some success / failure factors in the provision of public services by municipalities.
	<p>A clear example of failure is the waste management model in the Community of Madrid, which affects a multitude of municipalities. The strategy currently being followed is local, at best, at the joint level between municipalities. However, the definition of the strategy needs to be done at a higher, national (or even European) level.</p> <p>However, there are also examples of success in the provision of municipal public services. This has been seen clearly after the COVID-19 pandemic, where it has been seen that municipalities are the first administrations to respond, those that solve many of the problems more immediately and those that are more accessible when it comes to meet the needs of citizens.</p> <p>Another failure is, in general, the challenge of digitization. The development of these policies has two problems: time (it takes too long) and financial resources (lack of funding). Without going any further, there are many tasks that are carried out within a City Council that can be perfectly mechanized through information technologies.</p>
5	In your opinion, to what extent does the size of the municipality affect the provision of local public services?
	The size of the municipality has a major impact on the provision of services. In the first place, because economies of scale are fundamental in this matter. But, in addition, there are other factors beyond simple size. For the same population, a very relevant differential factor is the availability of economic resources: where there is more money there are more possibilities to provide better services. In this way, the smaller the municipality and the lower its economic resources, the more difficult it is to provide public services.
6	Do you understand that the current demand for local services adjusts to the current competences of the municipalities?

¹ This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 823961.

Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay¹.

H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018. Grant Agreement no. 823961

	<p>Not at all. Competences have been transferred to the municipalities, but the funding has subsequently been withdrawn to provide the services that these competencies carry with them. This was revealed with Law 27/2013 when it was intended to eradicate the so-called duplication of powers. It was then that the Autonomous Communities saw that these implied financial disbursements that the City Councils made to date, precisely by virtue of these transfers of authority.</p> <p>In general, the catalog of municipal competitions is outdated. There are some that must be attributed to higher levels of government and others that must be transferred to the municipality, and that are currently carried out by other Administrations.</p>
7	<p>In particular, do you understand that the role of municipalities should be increased in any specific area?</p> <p>7.2. And in environmental services?</p> <p>7.3. What about the power supply?</p>
	<p>Yes. A clear example is urban planning, where municipalities have more to contribute than they do now. And it is also necessary for the Autonomous Communities to be more agile and provide greater legal security.</p> <p>With regard to environmental services, each Administration must play the role that corresponds to it according to its area of competence in each specific area. Municipalities should not be given more relevance in the supply of energy, which should be something planned at a higher level.</p> <p>The increase in municipal powers in economic matters should also be studied. It is not well known what are the competences of the municipalities in this area. The Community of Madrid operates with collaboration agreements that perhaps should be converted into delegations or attributions of powers.</p>
8	<p>Currently, local legislation establishes mandatory local services in various sections of the population: up to 5,000 inhabitants, between 5,000 and 20,000 inhabitants, between 20,000 and 50,000 and more than 250,000 inhabitants. Do you understand that this segmentation is adequate or should be modified and in what sense?</p>
	<p>It is logical and correct that mandatory local services are segmented according to the population of the municipality, since this is directly related to the resources available to the</p>

¹ This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 823961.

Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay¹.

H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018. Grant Agreement no. 823961

	<p>municipality (together with the availability of economic resources). Another thing is that this specific segmentation is correct, and it is not. The provision of public services in a municipality of 20,000 inhabitants is nothing like the provision in one of 45,000, and yet the mandatory services are the same. These intervals should be further adjusted.</p>
--	---

Part B: Questions on Specific Practices

DIGITALISATION OF RURAL AREAS FOR THE DELIVERY OF PUBLIC SERVICES

9	<p>Is there in the Colmenar Viejo City Council (or the Community of Madrid) any specific initiative on digitization and local public services? If yes, which one / it is?</p>
	<p>In the Community of Madrid, he does not know it. At the Colmenar Viejo City Council, he has personally promoted some projects such as digitization and mechanization of processes (project in progress). The problem is that there is no general, common or long-term strategy at any level (state, regional or local). Isolated actions are made without a vision of the whole.</p>
10	<p>To what extent, until now, have the initial objectives been achieved?</p>
	<p>To the extent that there is no strategy, there are no clear objectives to be achieved. In the isolated actions that have been carried out, greater efficiency, accessibility and transparency in municipal management have been achieved.</p>
11	<p>In particular, to what extent has the efficient and transparent provision of certain local public services been improved?</p>
	<p>A very clear example of this is the digitization of the Administration's operation: electronic file, online document manager, paperless policy. The experience has been and continues to be very positive. Access and accessibility to information has been greatly facilitated not only for municipal managers, but also for citizens through the electronic headquarters of the City Council.</p>

¹ This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 823961.

Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay¹.

H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018. Grant Agreement no. 823961

12	Are there differences in the evaluation of the efficiency and transparency of the different local public services included?
	Not applicable.
13	To what extent has this project promoted innovation?
	The entire internal administrative functioning of the municipality has been completely modernized.
14	To what extent has this project improved or can it improve the quality of life of the population in a sustainable way?
	It affects directly. The citizen is much closer to municipal management: he can consult the updated regulations, make arrangements and consult information quickly, legal certainty and proximity.
15	To what extent does this project contribute and can it contribute to the maintenance of the population in rural areas?
	Here too there is a direct impact. One of the historical reasons for the rural exodus to the cities is that it was easier to find all the necessary services there. When physical proximity to certain poles (single administrations, work centers) is no longer necessary, there are greater incentives to stay in the cities, provided that public services are provided with equal or similar efficiency.
16	To what extent has this project created and has the potential to create business opportunities in rural areas that attract population?
	All digitization measures contribute to reducing the need to be or go to large capitals such as Madrid. In this measure, an increase in the population in rural or medium-sized municipalities can be encouraged, which logically creates greater business opportunities where that population sits.
17	In particular, is there already evidence - albeit preliminary - that allows the evaluation of social and economic results, such as in terms of cost reduction and new business opportunities?

¹ This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 823961.

Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay¹.

H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018. Grant Agreement no. 823961

	The measures implemented in the Madrid City Council do not have a specific empirical evaluation system. However, there is clear evidence of its positive results. The streamlining of procedures and the implementation of electronic administration have freed up time and human resources that used to be in charge of these tasks (a simple example is the time previously used in the general register of the City Council, which is now done mechanically through of the electronic office).
18	To what extent is inter-administrative cooperation necessary for the execution of this project? If so, is it developing properly?
	In general, the public administrations have to go hand in hand, also the city councils. To promote these measures, better legislative development is necessary. In addition, they depend to a great extent on the will of each City Council and the technical knowledge available, which generates many inequalities. If there were a national or regional strategy, the selection would be more correct and efficient, because already with a previous selection of some digital service providers, the information costs of the City Councils (especially the small ones) are greatly reduced. This is especially relevant in these areas due to the de facto dependence that arises once you start working with one of these providers, since it is very difficult to change all the systems from one to another.
19	What are the next lines of action planned in relation to this project? Will it affect new public services?
	There is work going on a study of all the processes and procedures that the City Council Secretariat must carry out to rationalize and, above all, digitally mechanize those processes whose nature allows it. It is expected to affect the entire operation of the municipal administration.
20	Are there other similar digitization projects being planned or planned for implementation?
	It has been answered previously.

DEMOGRAPHY AND POPULATION MOVEMENTS

¹ This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 823961.

Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay¹.

H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018. Grant Agreement no. 823961

21	Do you consider that the provision of public services influences the migratory flow to large cities? How? Can you provide an example?
	Altogether it does influence. The rural exodus is caused precisely by a greater provision of services in cities than in rural areas. Before, the needs for public services were perhaps lower, but today more services are demanded.
22	Does the aging of the population affect the provision of public services? what extent?
	Modulate what services are to be provided. Before, demographics were marked by birth rates, and public services followed this trend. Today there is a large retired population (not necessarily older) that requests other different services.
23	What other demographic changes affect the delivery of public services?
	Factors such as economic profile, origin, etc.
24	To what extent does the dispersion of the population affect the provision of public services?
	Directly. It is the worst situation in which a municipality can find itself: it has to repeat the same services and infrastructures as many times as there are urban centers within its municipal term. This multiplies the direct economic costs and creates many organizational problems.
25	To what extent does the dispersion of the population affect the choice of management methods?
	It is not one of the relevant factors to choose a form of management, at least as a general rule. Although it could be possible to achieve greater economies of scale (and thus more efficiency) by outsourcing a service performed by a company whose characteristics and size allow it to provide the service in various population centers without entailing inefficiencies (for example, urban waste collection).
26	In order to promote the development of rural municipalities, what are the most efficient forms of public service management? Can you provide an example? And what would be the most effective forms of management for this purpose?

¹ This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 823961.

Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay¹.

H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018. Grant Agreement no. 823961

	It has already been answered.
27	In order to attract or retain the population to rural municipalities, which offer of municipal services do you consider would be more favorable?
	The key is communication services (access with public and private transport) and telecommunications. A reasonably close offer of basic healthcare services (health center and schools and institutes, among others) is also necessary.

Part C: Additional Country-Specific Questions

FORMS OF PUBLIC SERVICE MANAGEMENT AND DELIVERY

28	Do you know which are the most used forms of local public service management in your territory?
	The most common form is outsourcing through public contracts (parks and gardens, waste, cleaning of buildings, works ...). In the absence of a public contract, it is usual for the service to be managed directly (social services, for example).
29	Do you know which are the forms of management of local public services most used in your territory in municipalities with less than 20,000 inhabitants? And in municipalities with less than 5,000 inhabitants?
	As far as I know, the most common form is indirect management through public contracts. In the Community of Madrid this is the rule outside the capital, with the possible exception of Rivas-Vaciamadrid.
30	How do you assess the choice and efficiency of the aforementioned forms of management?
	Outsourcing is much more efficient than direct management of public services by the Administration itself. It is the most efficient of the management models out there.

¹ This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 823961.

Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay¹.

H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018. Grant Agreement no. 823961

31	What forms of management do you consider most appropriate for the provision of local public services in municipalities between 5,000 and 20,000 inhabitants? And in municipalities with less than 5,000 inhabitants?
	Indirect management (outsourcing), at least as long as the Basic Statute of Public Employees is not substantially modified.
32	Compare, from the point of view of the provision of public services in municipalities with less than 20,000 inhabitants, the efficiency of the following options: 13.1. the forms of direct management and forms of indirect (contractual) management. 13.2. the forms of direct management by the municipal services themselves, and direct management through local commercial companies. 13.3. Direct management through local public companies and through mixed companies.
	13.1. The contractual route is more efficient. 13.2. do not have enough experience to assess it. 13.3. do not have enough experience to assess it.
33	What role does supramunicipal management (be it through the province, associations, other forms of cooperation) play in the provision of public services, especially in rural areas?
	It is of great help to small municipalities, but it can lead to a significant limitation of local organizational autonomy. In the example of urban waste and municipalities in Madrid, it is the Autonomous Community that determines practically everything related to the form of management.

¹ This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 823961.